

Resilience and Behaviour in Complex Position Navigation and Timing (PNT) Socio-Technical Systems

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Abstract

Positioning, Navigation and Timing (PNT) services underpin critical infrastructures including finance, energy, transport, and communications. However, the prevailing approaches to “Resilient PNT” remain dominated by technology-centric narratives: adding more signals, more layers and more independent systems. Industry and policy documents frequently equate resilience with the number and diversity of PNT sources or architectural complexity, rather than with the behaviour of systems and organisations under disruption.

Building on resilience thinking, panarchy¹ concepts, operational resilience modelling, and resilience engineering, this paper argues that resilience should be framed and engineered as behaviour over time in complex socio-technical systems such as those relying on PNT information, not as a static property of hardware. A requirements hierarchy is proposed in which resilience is specified as behavioural commitments under threat, grounded in threat scenarios, and system context. These commitments are then parameterised and only subsequently mapped to technology portfolios.

Implications for PNT specialists, business continuity managers and public decision-makers are discussed, advocating a shift from “What technology should we buy?” to “What behaviours must our systems execute, of what, to what, at what scale, and within what temporal bounds?”.

1 Introduction

Modern societies depend critically on accurate, reliable, and trustable PNT services. Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS)-derived signals support synchronisation in telecommunications and finance, enable navigation in aviation and maritime domains, and provide timing references for power grids and digital infrastructure [1]. Disruption to PNT information can propagate rapidly across sectors, creating systemic risks.

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¹Panarchy describes how complex systems can be understood when operating at different temporal and spatial scales

As awareness of this dependency has grown, so has the rhetoric of “Resilient PNT”. National and sectoral strategies, as well as vendor materials, routinely call for layered architectures, independent terrestrial backups, and multi-sensor fusion as the path to resilience [2][3]. Typical recommendations include “at least two or three sources of PNT”, “combined space and terrestrial architectures without common dependencies”, and “multi-layered solutions including GPS M-code, Galileo PRS, anti-jamming protection, inertial solutions, and alternative sensors” [4].

These measures have value, but they embody a particular mental model: resilience is achieved primarily by adding or diversifying technologies. This view risks conflating the enablers of resilience with the resilience itself. As resilience thinking in ecology and socio-ecological systems has emphasised, resilience is fundamentally about how systems absorb, adapt to and recover from disturbances over time, and must be defined in relation to specific systems, disturbances and scales—“resilience of what, to what?” [5][6][7].

This paper applies this broader concept to PNT. It argues that “Resilient PNT” cannot be adequately understood as an inventory of signals and boxes. Instead, resilience emerges from the behaviours of interconnected technical and organisational subsystems—human operators, algorithms, procedures, governance structures—across multiple scale. These are socio-technical systems [8]. Technology provides the affordances within which those behaviours occur.

To develop this argument, Section 2 introduces theoretical foundations from resilience thinking, panarchy, operational resilience and resilience engineering. Section 3 frames PNT resilience behaviourally and proposes a requirements hierarchy grounded in Carpenter’s “of what, to what” formulation [6]. Section 4 presents a parametric template for behavioural resilience requirements, aligning it with the *TNLC* structure used in operational resilience modelling [9][10]. Section 5 uses a resilience curve representation and panarchy concepts to explore cross-level behaviour in PNT systems [11]. Section 6 discusses implications for design, procurement, governance, and business continuity.

2 Theoretical Foundations

Resilience thinking emerged in ecology to characterise the capacity of systems to absorb disturbances and reorganise while undergoing change, retaining as far as possible the same function, structure, identity, and feedbacks [12]. Carpenter and colleagues emphasised that meaningful resilience analysis must begin by specifying resilience *of what, to what?*: the particular system of interest and the disturbances or stresses of concern [6].

Panarchy

The concept of panarchy describes how complex systems can be understood as nested adaptive cycles operating at different temporal and spatial scales [11]. Each level (e.g., device, infrastructure, sector, national policy) undergoes phases of growth, accumulation, collapse and reorganisation. Cross-scale interactions—such as fast variables at lower levels triggering slow reconfigurations at higher levels—are central to system behaviour.

For PNT, a panarchy view suggests that resilience cannot be treated solely at the device or single-system layer. For example, aggressive local failover rules in different PNT sources in use, if uncoordinated, may overload or present incorrect data to a fusion function, or a downstream system, when a GNSS outage occurs—increasing overall system fragility. Conversely policy decisions about spectrum allocation or backup infrastructure provisioning at national level, may strongly condition

what is possible for local operators.

Integrating panarchy into PNT resilience analysis encourages explicit consideration of which scales are being made more resilient, at the possible expense of others, and how behavioural requirements at one level interact with capacities at other levels.

Operational Resilience and the TNLC Framework

Ganin, Linkov, and colleagues propose an operational resilience framework where systems are represented as networks whose performance over time under disruption can be analysed and compared [13][6][9][14][11][10].

A generic representation uses four key sets of variables:

$$Resilience(t) = \left(\prod_{i=1}^T K(N, L, C, t_i) \right)^{\frac{1}{T}} \quad (1)$$

System performance at any instance in time (t) is represented by K ; T represents the time steps or discrete stages in the scenario; and N equates to the number of nodes or components of the system. The links between the nodes, including their weights and states are represented by L . C is the set of control and decision rules—i.e., how the system behaves, including its adaptation strategies.

Resilience is then assessed via performance trajectories $K(t)$ that show how system performance degrades and recovers following a disruption. The framework emphasises that while N and L influence system design and failure modes, C —the operational decision rules—often has the largest impact on resilience outcomes, because they govern detection, response and recovery [9][11].

For PNT systems, this mapping is natural: T corresponds to the temporal resolution of monitoring, detection, decision-making and control actions in PNT operations; N includes PNT sources (GNSS constellations, terrestrial signals), user platforms, distribution networks, clocks and control centres; L represents physical, logical and organisational dependencies: e.g., redundancy type, communications links, power supplies, data flows, contractual and regulatory relationships; and C encompasses automated failover logic, human operating procedures, alarm thresholds, escalation paths and recovery playbooks.

This *TNLC* structure provides a bridge between abstract resilience modelling and concrete PNT design choices.

Resilience Engineering and Systems that can Learn and Adapt (i.e., "Systems of the Fourth Kind")

Resilience engineering, as developed by Hollnagel, focuses on how socio-technical systems succeed under varying conditions [15]. He characterises resilience not as a static property, but as a set of four abilities:

1. Anticipate: foresee potential disruptions and opportunities.
2. Monitor: track relevant system and environmental conditions.
3. Respond: act effectively when disturbances occur.
4. Learn: incorporate experience into changed structure or behaviour.

He uses these abilities to define different types of system, based on their ability, and the fourth type “systems of the fourth kind”, encompasses all of the attributes and abilities noted here. These “fourth kind” systems are open, adaptive socio-technical systems that cannot be fully described or controlled in classical engineering terms. These systems exhibit performance variability; resilience lies in managing that variability, not eliminating it [16][17].

PNT infrastructures and their dependent domains (e.g., air traffic management, financial clearing systems) are prime examples of such systems. Operators, regulators, vendors, and users form a web of interactions that cannot be reduced to hardware performance alone. In this context, resilience engineering argues for designing and managing behaviours—including human and organisational behaviours—that sustain their function during and after disruptions, especially considering the operational independence of systems and their likely asynchronous lifecycles.

3 Behaviour-Centric PNT Resilience

Synthesising the above, PNT resilience can be defined behaviourally as:

The ability of PNT-enabled socio-technical systems to sustain required services for defined stakeholders, under expected and unexpected conditions, by detecting disruptions, responding and adapting within specified temporal and performance bounds, and learning in ways that improve future responses across relevant scales.

This definition makes explicit:

- The system of interest (“of what”): PNT-enabled services and infrastructures.
- The disturbances (“to what”): jamming, spoofing, environmental and internal failures.
- The behaviours: anticipate, monitor/detect, respond, recover, and learn/adapt.
- The temporal bounds: how quickly actions must occur.
- The multi-scale nature: behaviours at device, organisational and policy levels, including understanding how any system adaptations impact the environment in which the system is operating.
- The set of stakeholders that the system is delivering capability for (“for whom”).

Technology appears implicitly as an enabler or constraint on these behaviours, not as the primary locus of resilience. From this standpoint, a PNT resilience requirements hierarchy can be articulated, as shown in Figure 1 as:

1. Context and scope (Carpenter’s question): - Resilience *of what* (which PNT-dependent services, for which stakeholders)? - Resilience *to what* (which threats, disturbances, failure modes)? - At *what scales* (device, system, sector, national) and *for whom*?
2. System resilience requirements (behavioural commitments under threat): For each defined scenario, specify required detection, response, and recovery behaviours and timeframes.
 - (a) System requirements and derived quality requirements: Service definitions (e.g., timing accuracy, position availability) under normal conditions.
 - (b) Derived behavioural quality requirements: Detection sensitivity and thresholds, maximum allowable degradation (e.g., timing error, positional uncertainty) during response and recovery, and recovery time to acceptable performance.
 - (c) Function-specific resilience requirements: Resistance/robustness (e.g., holdover capability), detection (monitoring, anomaly detection), response (failover strategies, reconfiguration), and recovery (reacquisition, validation, normalisation).
3. Specific system or sub-system quality requirements: performance, functional and non-functional requirements (e.g., coverage, time-to-first-fix, sensitivity, integrity (although it can be argued

Figure 1: Requirements Hierarchy, including behavioural aspects

integrity can constitute a resilience requirement), data rate, size, weight, power consumption, and cost profile)

4. Technology and architecture choices: Selection and configuration of GNSS, alternative PNT, inertial sensors, clocks, networks and control systems to satisfy 2 & 3 at acceptable cost and complexity.

This hierarchy explicitly places behavioural requirements before technology selection. It also embeds panarchy and resilience engineering notions by incorporating multiple scales and human/organisational factors into the early steps.

4 Parametric Behavioural Requirements

To make behavioural resilience requirements concrete and testable, they can be expressed using a generic parametric template:

In operational mode M for threat scenario S , the system shall:

- Detect with a probability of W , more than $P\%$ of relevant adverse events within Y seconds.
- Limit performance degradation of capability X to less than $D\%$ during response.
- Recover capability X to within threshold Th within R seconds of threat cessation.
- Achieve these outcomes with probability greater than Q over specified test conditions.

In a PNT context:

- Detect, with a probability of 0.99, a loss or corruption of GNSS timing, within 2s.
- Limit timing error over nominal to $1\mu\text{s}$ and switch to disciplined local oscillators and/or terrestrial timing within 1s of detection.
- Limit timing error to less than 100ns during backup mode.
- Recover GNSS-based timing within 30s of GNSS loss ceasing, with 0.99 probability.

Bringing these together at a conceptual level, P might quantify the proportion of jamming or spoofing events that must be detected, the types of threat/disruption, or a description of the impact of

a disruption to account for unknown (as the design time) threats or disruptions. Y captures detection latency (e.g., 2s for jamming affecting timing in financial systems); D expresses acceptable degradation (e.g., timing error may increase to 100ns, or positional error to 10m, during backup mode) and R sets recovery time (e.g., 20–30 s to restore primary GNSS service) to a minimum performance threshold Th . Finally, W and Q expresses confidence requirements (e.g., 0.99 probability under representative conditions).

Consider a simplified GNSS jamming scenario affecting a financial timing service: *Of what?* Timing distribution for high-frequency trading platforms in a national market. *To what?* Localised, intentional GNSS jamming near key data centres.

These parameters translate high-level resilience aspirations into operationally meaningful commitments, which can be tested under controlled conditions. Technology options—types of oscillators, alternative timing sources, detection algorithms—are chosen, and can be modified in a repeatable manner, to satisfy these behavioural parameters, rather than being specified a priori as “resilience measures”.

Alignment with TNLC

The parametric template aligns naturally with the *TNLC* framework:

- *T*: The detection and recovery times Y and R specify temporal performance constraints. They inform required sampling rates, decision cycles and control loop designs.
- *N*: The acceptable degradation D and target capability X depend partly on what components exist and how many (e.g., number of clocks and alternative PNT inputs), but adding nodes without changing behavioural parameters does not alter resilience guarantees.
- *L*: Achievability of P , D , R , W , Q is conditioned by link structure and dependencies. E.g., if backup PNT signals share a common power or communications dependency with primaries, or if certain threat scenarios may violate assumptions.
- *C*: Most critically, P , Y , D , R , W , Q are implemented through decision rules: thresholds for anomaly detection, logic for switching between modes, conditions for declaring recovery, and operator escalation procedures.

Thus, while TN and L describe structure, the parametric requirements sit primarily in C , emphasising that **resilience is altered most effectively by changing decision rules and behaviours, not simply by increasing the number of sources.**

5 Resilience Curves and Panarchy in PNT

Single-level Resilience Curve

Following Ayyub and Linkov, resilience can be visualised as a performance curve $K(t)$ over time, per Figure 2 [18][11]. For a single PNT-enabled system:

- Before disruption, performance $K(t)$ is near 100%.
- When a threat occurs (e.g., jamming onset), performance declines as errors grow or service is temporarily lost.
- Detection and response actions shape the depth and duration of this decline.
- Recovery actions shape the slope of performance restoration to acceptable levels.

Figure 2: Resilience Curve, derived from [18], [11]

The integral under the curve relative to a baseline can be used as a quantitative resilience metric, but the key design insight is qualitative: the shape of the curve is governed by behaviour, not by source count alone.

Nested Curves and Cross-Scale Effects

In a panarchy perspective, multiple such curves exist at different levels: Device level: individual receivers or platforms responding to signal anomalies; System level: organisational services (e.g., a timing distribution network) responding to device-level issues; Sector level: e.g., a financial market or air traffic control region responding to system-level degradations; and National or regional level: policy and regulatory responses, activation of national backup capabilities.

Behavioural requirements at one level interact with capabilities and constraints at others. For example:

- Device-level failover to a terrestrial PNT system, triggered by conservative thresholds, may cause a surge in demand on that backup system, risking overload or unanticipated interference with other users.
- Sector-level business continuity plans may assume that alternative PNT is always available, while national-level provisioning may have designed that backup only for limited critical loads.

This highlights the importance of specifying behavioural resilience requirements not only at the device or single-system level, but also for cross-scale interactions, and for the different disruption scenarios (playbooks) the system will face. Carpenter’s “of what, to what, at what scale, and for whom?” become critical in PNT planning [6].

Changing "C" vs. Adding "N"

Within this multi-level view, the earlier maxim—to alter resilience, change C , not N —takes on richer meaning: At the device level, changing C might mean more sophisticated anomaly detection, better-tuned thresholds, or adaptive filtering strategies. At the system level, it might mean redesigning failover playbooks, operator training, and escalation paths. At sector level, it could involve coordinated protocols for load-sharing across alternative PNT services or temporary relaxation of performance

requirements. At the policy level, it might mean revised exercises, standards and regulatory expectations that emphasise behavioural performance over simple redundancy metrics.

Figure 3 shows different profile resilience curves where different operational behaviours/decision rules are shown (different values of C) which can clearly show that a faster response results in a higher resilience profile, and that a larger performance degradation increases overall system failure (towards a performance output of zero) risk. Clearly the profile in Figure 3a represents the most desirable system response to a disruption, although cost modelling will clearly play a part in the final choices made.

Figure 3: Changing C changes the curve shape to deliver differing system profiles

Adding more sources (N) without coherent changes in decision rules (C) risks producing complex but fragile systems.

6 Implications for Practice

For PNT Engineers and Architects

PNT specialists should treat resilience requirements as first-class behavioural specifications, not as implicit by-products of architectural choices. Design processes should:

1. Begin with explicit “of what, to what” formulations for relevant stakeholders and services.
2. Define scenario-specific parametric requirements (detection time, degradation bounds, recovery time, success probability).
3. Map these parameters onto *TNLC*, recognising that most levers lie in C : control logic, algorithms, and procedures.
4. Use resilience curves to visualise and compare candidate architectures and decision rules, not only hardware redundancy.

For Business Continuity Managers

Business continuity managers should view PNT resilience as an integral part of operational resilience, expressed in the same behavioural language used for other critical services. Behavioural PNT requirements can be integrated into business impact analyses and continuity plans, but first a few key questions have to be asked:

- How long can we tolerate degraded timing or positioning, and with what consequences?
- How quickly must we detect problems to avoid unacceptable impacts?
- What coordination is needed across sites, sectors and scales?
- How often are realistic scenarios tested and exercised?

This helps align technical PNT planning with organisational risk appetites and regulatory expectations.

For Policymakers and Regulators

Policy frameworks and standards often default to specifying technologies (e.g., “independent backup PNT”, “multi-constellation receivers”). A behaviour-centric approach suggests that policies should instead:

- Mandate behavioural resilience performance (e.g., detection and recovery times under defined threat scenarios)
- Encourage cross-sector exercises that test behavioural requirements across scales (panarchy in practice)
- Recognise resilience engineering as an ongoing governance activity, not a one-off technical fix.

By focusing on behaviours and temporal performance, policies become more robust to technological change and vendor claims, and can better support informed public debate about acceptable levels of PNT dependency and risk.

7 Conclusion

This paper has argued that many contemporary treatments of “Resilient PNT” are overly technology-centric, equating resilience with the number and diversity of PNT sources or the complexity of architectures. Drawing on resilience thinking, panarchy, operational resilience and resilience engineering, PNT resilience has been reframed as behaviour over time in complex socio-technical systems.

Carpenter’s “of what, to what?” question was used to ground PNT resilience analysis in specific systems, disturbances, scales and stakeholders. Ganin and Linkov’s *TNLC* framework was mapped to PNT components and decision structures, emphasising the central role of operational decision rules (*C*) in shaping resilience curves and outcomes. Hollnagel’s resilience engineering perspective highlighted that resilience resides in the ability to anticipate, monitor, respond and learn, particularly in “systems of the fourth kind” where human and organisational factors are integral.

A behavioural requirements hierarchy, a parametric template for resilience specifications, and a multi-level resilience curve interpretation were presented, showing how PNT systems can be designed, procured and governed based on behavioural commitments under threat rather than technology lists.

For PNT specialists, business continuity managers and policy-makers, the practical message is clear:

- **Resilience is not hardware**
- **Resilience is behaviour × time**

The systems that **detect faster, respond more intelligently and recover more effectively** will be more resilient, *regardless* of how many PNT sources they possess.

Future research and practice should concentrate on parameterising and validating these behaviours across scales, integrating resilience thinking and engineering more deeply into the design and governance of PNT-dependent infrastructures.

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